

AutoML in the Face of Adversity: Securing Mobility Predictions in NWDAF

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Abstract—Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is a key component in 5G networks, introduced by 3G Partnership Project (3GPP) standards, that leverages machine learning to optimize network performance. The 3GPP standards mandate that mobile network operators should retrain NWDAF models to maintain accuracy. However, the presence of adversarial user equipment (UE) can introduce corrupted data points during this retraining process, compromising prediction accuracy. Manually selecting optimal models for NWDAF tasks is challenging and time-consuming, making Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) an attractive solution. This paper investigates strategies for operators to maintain NWDAF model performance using AutoML in the face of adversarial attacks, focusing on mobility prediction. We consider two main retraining strategies: (A) reselecting the model using AutoML at each retraining and (B) retaining the initial model. We evaluate these strategies using different AutoML frameworks under varying proportions of adversarial UEs, assuming that the attacker is unaware of the retraining schedule and the operator lacks the capability to distinguish between adversarial and legitimate mobility patterns. Our results show that, in the presence of adversarial UEs, retraining with AutoML yields worse results compared to retaining a well-trained initial model selected using an extensive AutoML search during initial training. We, therefore, recommend that operators prioritize model selection during initial training, ensuring the base model is optimally tuned to maintain accuracy over subsequent retraining. This allows effective mobility prediction to be preserved even if corrupted data cannot be fully excluded.

Index Terms—NWDAF, 5G, adversarial mobility

I. INTRODUCTION

5G network has brought significant advancements in mobile technology, with the 3GPP introducing the NWDAF [1], [2] as a new component. NWDAF harnesses the power of machine learning (ML) to optimize network performance, enabling operators to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and improve user experience. However, the 3GPP standards require operators to periodically retrain NWDAF models to ensure continued accuracy, a task that can be complex and resource-intensive when done manually. AutoML has emerged as a promising

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solution, with recent reports [3], [4] highlighting its growing adoption in NWDAF deployments. One of the key applications of NWDAF is mobility trajectory prediction, which involves forecasting the future locations of user equipment (UE). Accurate mobility predictions are essential for optimizing network operations and resource allocation. For instance, by leveraging mobility predictions, operators can achieve significant reductions in paging signaling, leading to improved computational efficiency [5].

However, the presence of malicious UEs can compromise the integrity of the NWDAF retraining process by injecting corrupted data points. While previous research [6] has demonstrated the detrimental impact of adversarial mobility on prediction accuracy during the inference phase, this paper takes a step further by investigating the effects of adversarial attacks on the training data itself. We focus on scenarios where malicious UEs evade detection until the retraining phase, corrupting the data used to update the NWDAF models. In our study, we assume that the attacker is unaware of the operator’s retraining schedule and that the operator lacks the capability to distinguish between adversarial and legitimate mobility patterns.

The 3GPP standards recognize the potential threat posed by abnormal UEs and mandate that operators implement mechanisms to identify and exclude their data to maintain the accuracy of NWDAF analytics (3GPP 23.288 [1], section 5.1). However, given the challenges associated with anomaly detection, even the presence of such mechanisms may not guarantee the identification of all malicious activities within the network. This paper delves into the challenge of maintaining NWDAF model performance in the face of adversarial attacks that evade detection, focusing on the role of AutoML in discovering robust models.

We explore two primary retraining strategies for operators to mitigate the impact of adversarial attacks: (A) employing AutoML to reselect the model at each retraining iteration and (B) retaining the initial model discovered by AutoML. We assess the effectiveness of these strategies using various AutoML frameworks and under different levels of adversarial UE presence. Our findings reveal that, in the presence of adversarial UEs, retraining with AutoML yields worse results compared to retaining a well-trained initial model selected using an extensive AutoML search during initial training.

The main contributions of this paper are twofold:

- We conduct an in-depth investigation into the impact of adversarial UEs on the AutoML model selection process for NWDAF mobility prediction, considering scenarios where operators rely on AutoML for model discovery and lack the capability to distinguish between adversarial and legitimate mobility patterns.
- Based on our analysis, we provide recommendations on the most effective strategy for operators to maintain NWDAF model accuracy in the presence of adversarial UEs, focusing on the trade-offs between retraining with AutoML and retaining a well-trained initial model.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II surveys related work on AutoML, mobility prediction, and adversarial machine learning. Section III provides an overview of the NWDAF model lifecycle and the problem statement. Section IV describes the operator retraining strategies considered in this study. Section V presents the threat model. Section VI details the modeling of UE mobility. Section VII discusses the simulation setup and results. Finally, Section VIII concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Below, we discuss the most relevant related work. We will cover previous work on AutoML with a particular focus on open frameworks. Next, we discuss previous work on ML-based mobility prediction and, finally, adversarial machine learning.

A. Automated Machine Learning (AutoML)

AutoML [7] has gained significant attention in recent years due to the increasing demand for ML solutions and the shortage of experts [8]. It is designed to automate the process of building machine learning models, including tasks such as data preprocessing, feature engineering, model selection, and hyperparameter tuning [9], [10]. Numerous approaches have been proposed in the literature to achieve this goal, such as genetic algorithms [11], Bayesian optimization [12], and cost frugal optimization [13]. It is particularly well suited for telecom operators, especially small ones, where AI is not the focus, and acquiring such expertise might take time, effort, and money. While previous research has provided a benchmark on different AutoML frameworks [14], the result was from general datasets and runs on a malignant environment. Our work focuses on exploring AutoML for mobility data in mobile operators while adversarial data is introduced to the environment simultaneously.

TABLE I
EMPLOYED AUTOML FRAMEWORKS IN THE EXPERIMENTS.

Framework	Optimization and Search Space
Auto-sklearn [15]	Bayesian Optimization
Autogluon [16]	Stacked Ensembles of Preset Pipelines
FLAML [17]	Cost Frugal Optimization

Given the excessive costs involved in assessing every framework, we chose to focus on analyzing three specific frameworks for this study from table I, i.e., Auto-sklearn [15], Autogluon [16], and FLAML [17]. We focus on finding a generalized conclusion on how the AutoML solution would handle when the training data is poisoned with adversarial data points, particularly in the context of NWDAF in 5G.

Each of the frameworks listed above employs unique strategies: Auto-sklearn employs Bayesian optimization [12], and AutoGluon [16] employs multiple techniques, i.e., ensembling and stacking [18] for model performance enhancement, alongside multi-fidelity optimization [19] and bandit-based resource allocation [20] for efficient model selection. It also utilizes Neural Architecture Search (NAS) [21] for optimizing models to balance performance and search efficiency. FLAML is a lightweight AutoML tool that employs an adaptive ensemble learning approach to construct high-performing models with minimal computational overhead [13].

B. ML-based mobility prediction

In the area of ML-based mobility prediction and its resource application in 5G, several works have been proposed. The existing works can be roughly categorized into two groups: traditional ML-based [22]–[24], and deep learning-based [25], [26]. An example of the former is a new framework for 5G using Random Forest to improve its resource allocation efficiency and robustness [22]. Additionally, [24] introduces an approach for predicting node mobility in mobile ad hoc networks using Extreme Learning Machines (ELMs) [27]. For the latter approaches, in [25], Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) was employed for traffic prediction in vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs). The authors of [26] proposed a low-cost approach to mobility prediction in 5G using a deep learning model based on the user’s previous location and velocity data.

C. Adversarial Machine Learning

Relative to the stages of learning, a report from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [28] classifies the attack toward machine learning model into two categories: (i) Training-time attacks and (ii) Deployment-time attacks. The common term of the former is poisoning attack [29], which can be classified into two categories: data poisoning [29], [30] where an attacker injects harmful data into the training set and model poisoning [31] where the attacker tampers with the model itself, either during training or via a compromised update mechanism. The latter can also be classified into two categories: evasion attack [32]–[34], where the adversary modifies input data to cause the machine learning model to make incorrect predictions, and privacy attack [35], [36] where the aim is to extract sensitive information from the model or its data. While the work against a deployed NWDAF model [6] is considered to be an evasion attack, our work in this paper focuses on data poisoning attacks.

Fig. 1. The lifecycle of NWDAF's model

III. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

A. Background: The Lifecycle of an NWDAF Model

The NWDAF model is defined by 3GPP [1]. It is a rather broad framework allowing different mobile network analytics functions to be implemented. The standard also discusses a mechanism for identifying abnormal UEs. There is a mandatory requirement for the operator to have the means to distinguish such abnormality within a given time window and potentially exclude their data to maintain the accuracy of NWDAF analytics (3GPP 23.288 [1], section 5.1). As anomaly detection is challenging, even if such a mechanism exists, it cannot detect all malicious activities in the network.

The life cycle of an NWDAF model following the standard [1] would typically look like the one we depict in Figure 1. Below, we explain the details of the different steps:

- C1 The cycle starts with an initial training (green) to generate the first version of the trajectory model. The model selection can be handcrafted manually or by using an automated mechanism with AutoML. In this paper, our approach follows the model selection of the prior work [6], which involves picking the best model with AutoML. Once the best model is identified, it is deployed to the live environment to provide services to other NFs in the network. The accuracy of the deployed model is periodically checked and remeasured every predefined period. A decrease in accuracy indicates either behavioral changes of legitimate UEs or the presence of adversarial UEs in the network.
- C2 In the presence of adversarial UEs in the network, the 3GPP standard mandates that the operator must have the means to distinguish the legitimate and adversarial UEs to be potentially excluded from the network (red).
- C3 If the accuracy is back to normal after the exclusion of adversarial UEs (C2), the NWDAF model continues its operation. Otherwise, the operator assumes that there is a shift in the (legitimate) user mobility behavior. When this happens, the assumed-to-be all benign UEs form the training set and will be used in the next retraining task (blue). This generates a new model that will be deployed to the live environment. Similar to the C1 situation, in this

phase, the model selection can be handcrafted manually, or AutoML can be used to automate the selection.

B. Problem Definition

In this paper, we assume the situation in step C2 where the operator is unable to exclude abnormal UEs from the dataset. This means the adversarial data points are included in the next retraining task in C3. This situation can, for instance, occur due to (i) a newer version of adversarial mobility is introduced to the network such that the defense mechanism fails to recognize, or (ii) a number of legitimate UEs turns into adversarial in the middle of NWDAF deployment in a way that the system believes that the UEs are still benign. When no proper anomaly detection exists, the NWDAF will train on all data, including any adversarial data points, and as a consequence, the adversarial data points will poison the dataset for the next retraining task in C3. The severity of this issue depends on (i) the type of adversarial mobility (previous work [6] has shown that different mobility affects the accuracy during inference in different ways) and (ii) the proportion of the adversarial data points in the dataset.

Given the data poisoning situation described above, we consider the problem of forming an operator retraining strategy in C3 that gives acceptable mobility prediction accuracy. The term acceptable here means that the accuracy for the legitimate user should not be decreased in any way. Even when it is, the decrement should be kept as small as possible to minimize the impact. In the context of the use of AutoML, we are particularly interested in whether the use of AutoML in C1 and C3 is suitable when the operator is enduring an attack from the adversarial UEs. This includes whether they need to employ AutoML at all times (both C1 and C3) or not. Using AutoML at all times is convenient, but we want to find the answer to whether using this strategy is robust enough in the long run, particularly when the number of adversarial data points increases. It is also important to notice that *if*, we can find a solution to this problem; there is not even a *need* to introduce any other type of anomaly detection into the system for this type of mobility attack, as the system will be robust *independent* of the presence of the attack or not; as long as the selected model is robust enough.

IV. DIFFERENT OPERATOR RETRAINING STRATEGIES

To address the identified research problem, we investigate two natural classes and three different types of hypothetical operator strategies based on the characteristics of their retraining profile in C3, i.e., how they use AutoML during retraining tasks. We denote the two classes, A and B, respectively, and the selection is based on a more general work about continual learning in practice [37]. But, before that, we explain the time budget in AutoML as it is the main factor for classifying the strategies.

A. Time-budget in AutoML

The term *time-budget* [38] refers to the maximum amount of time that the AutoML system is allowed to search for the

best machine learning model and its hyperparameters given the input dataset. Essentially, it sets a runtime limit on the AutoML process. However, searching through all possible combinations of models and their hyperparameters can be computationally expensive and time-consuming. While a more extended time budget can potentially lead to a more optimized model, it does not always guarantee significantly better performance. After a certain point, the improvements might be marginal. Hence, choosing an appropriate time budget is crucial to balance model performance and computational efficiency.

B. New model and data for each retraining

The first strategy, A, is about constantly updating the learning process as new data comes in. In [37], it is termed as a self-correction policy where “*the policy engine is responsible for updating models by triggering retraining or other actions*”. In our case, the trigger is a lowered accuracy after the system is assumed to have separated the adversarial data points from the dataset (which is actually not the case). With the model being updated for every trigger of the policy engine, AutoML is used to select the best model at all times (both during initial training and at retraining). Strategy A is formally defined as:

- A The operator selects the best model and hyperparameters both during initial training (C1) and during the retraining period (C3) using AutoML.

This is a natural and straightforward strategy to choose. In this case, setting an appropriate AutoML time budget is critical. Performing a retraining task using AutoML can be time-consuming, with a significant portion of time dedicated to finding the best model given the polluted dataset. In order to minimize the impact, a lower time budget is desirable. However, a lower time budget may result in a less accurate model and a poor selection of hyperparameters. Striking a balance between these two factors is crucial to achieving a performant model while keeping uptime high. The discussion to balance these two factors is explored in section VII-C.

C. Old model and new data for each retraining

The second strategy, B, is the opposite of the first one. It diverges from the continual learning ideal by limiting the scope of retraining. This reflects a practical compromise, as highlighted in [37], between the ideal of continuous model evolution and the realities of computational and resource constraints. According to the second strategy, the operator thinks model reselection using AutoML is costly (computation, time, and cost-wise). In this case, the operator’s natural choice is to select the initial model with AutoML but retrain using the same selected model as picked initially with newer data (which, in this case, might include the adversarial data points). We formally define strategy B as follows:

- B The operator selects the best model and hyperparameters with AutoML only during initial training (C1) and then retrains the same initial model and hyperparameters during the retraining period (C3) with newer data.

We divide this retraining strategy class into two different categories, depending on the allocated time budget for the initial training (C1):

- B1 Short time budget.
- B2 Long time budget.

For the strategies B1 and B2, as the operator decided to stick with the initial model, allocating more time budget is not a problem. This is because AutoML is only used when NWDAF is not yet deployed, and spending as much time as possible in finding a suitable model can be done without affecting the live deployment in any way. Hence, allocating a larger time budget is not as costly as in the first strategy. The main consideration is, instead, the computational cost, where a larger time budget means more resources are needed for the initial training.

V. THREAT MODEL

For a mobility attack to be considered feasible, it must not require an unreasonable amount of effort. In particular, an attack that involves moving UEs (physically) throughout the network for extended durations is not practical. The resources and effort needed to carry out such an attack would outweigh any potential gains, making these types of attacks improbable and beyond the scope of this analysis.

This study operates under the assumption that an adversary possesses the capability to obtain UEs and create multiple clones with identical International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) numbers. The attack can be scaled vertically by acquiring more UEs or horizontally by increasing the number of cloned UEs. The acquisition process can be either legitimate, following standard procedures, or illegitimate if existing ones are stolen. Note that this scaling is limited as assuming the adversary can control all the UEs in the network is not feasible. It means that the adversary does not have full white-box capabilities, as it only controls a small portion of the UEs in the network. Research has demonstrated the feasibility of extracting the main secret key from a 4G Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) [39], [40]. If the adversary gains access to the primary USIM key, they may be able to duplicate it. While NWDAF and our attack are mainly intended for 5G, we envision that a similar attack can be applied in a non-standalone 5G network.

Since our primary objective is to illustrate how the presence of adversarial UEs can also impact the accuracy of legitimate UEs’ trajectory prediction **if** the operator fails to exclude the adversarial UEs before the next retraining task, we assume that the adversarial mobility from the attacker cannot be detected in step C2, i.e., a data poisoning event has occurred. In such a worst-case scenario (given the attack that is performed), we explore what can be done to minimize the impact on the operator using the different identified strategies A, B1, and B2. In a real-world scenario, this situation often occurs when a newly formed adversarial pattern is introduced by the adversary, making the system unable to detect the attack. It should be noted that the mobility model itself is not a part of the NWDAF specification, as the 3GPP standard only defines

interfaces and use cases. However, we have defined a mobility model with NWDAF input and output.

VI. MOBILITY

A. Mobility Simulator

The privacy-sensitive nature of UE mobility data poses challenges to obtaining real-world data from mobile operators due to strict privacy laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [41]. To address this issue, Ericsson has developed an internal spatiotemporal mobility simulator [42] capable of producing UE mobility data based on predetermined mobility models. The spatial aspect of the simulator is based on a real-world deployment of Airtel’s open-network topology [43] in India. On top of that, the mobility data is generated as time series data that manifests UE connected to a particular eNodeB with calculated signal strength based on distance and the load of the respective eNodeB. Although the simulator is not open-sourced, a subset of the post-processed dataset is available in our repository: <https://github.com/nwdaf-research/dataset-attack>.

B. Prediction Accuracy

Mobility prediction in UE involves two crucial metrics: (1) location prediction at a specific time denoted as \hat{l} , and (2) timeslot prediction (\hat{s}) given that \hat{l} is accurate. The latter metric indicates how long a UE remains connected to a specific eNodeB at a particular time. For a given period of $t_2 - t_1 \in T$ with n mobility events e , the mobility prediction accuracy is calculated as the sum of correct timeslot predictions \hat{s} (when \hat{l} is correct) divided by the total number of predictions. The accuracy is shown in equation 1 and will be used throughout this paper.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_{e=0}^n (\hat{s}_{correct} | \hat{l}_{correct})}{n} \quad (1)$$

C. Legitimate Mobility

Generalizing UE mobility and providing a one-size-fits-all model to perform prediction is a non-trivial task [44]. This is due to the uniqueness of the mobility, either as an individual or as aggregates in a particular area. While some mobilities are too stochastic to enable reliable prediction, others may follow patterns that are possible to model. With this assumption, we decided to pick a subset of UE mobility called *working professional* [45] as the legitimate UEs in the dataset, which follows a periodic movement pattern between the office and the home. It assumes that professionals engage in regular movements between their residences and workplaces throughout the day and evening. The model employs randomly selected initial coordinates for home and office, adhering to specific location constraints. This mobility pattern is relevant in most areas worldwide. As our base installation of the eNodeB is based on an operator in India, this mobility represents the population of 140 million people based on Census data [46].

D. Adversarial Mobility

For adversarial mobility, the previous study [6] has shown one attack, called the tuple jump mobility attack, as the most effective in decreasing the NWDAF’s accuracy. We use this type of attack in our measurement. To do this, the attacker divides the adversarial UEs into pairs and assigns each pair the same IMSI (original and cloned), allowing them to impersonate each other. Within each pair, the adversary can make one device connect to an eNodeB while the other remains silent, then switch their roles in the next step, creating the appearance of movement between different locations while actually both of them stay in their locations at all times. The attacker makes the choice of eNodeBs randomly and can include geographically distant ones. This attack can be carried out without much effort since the devices can be placed near the chosen eNodeBs and do not need to move physically, fulfilling the requirement from the adversary in our threat model. When an adversary obtains multiple UEs, they can use this technique to confuse the network operator and make it seem like a single device is moving erratically between different eNodeBs.

VII. SIMULATION AND RESULT

A. Simulation Environment

The UE mobility simulation and the computation to find the best model, followed by attacking such a model, was conducted on a server with 48 cores of AMD EPYC 7413 and 256 GB of memory. While the number of adversarial UEs varied between 50 and 1000 (with an increment of 50), the simulation included a baseline of 10,000 legitimate UEs. The simulation spanned five days, with the first four days used for training and the final day for testing.

B. Data Preprocessing

This work utilized a dataset sourced from the mobility simulator mentioned in section VI-A, containing three main features: {IMSI, eNodeB_path, signal_strength}. The data contains historically connected eNodeBs coupled with each connection’s timestamp and signal strength for a particular unique IMSI. Table II shows an IMSI 08126630, which is historically connected to eNodeB 2 and 17 at timestamp 99 and 244, respectively, where the signal strength of each connection is 0.154 and 0.199.

TABLE II
RAW DATA

IMSI	eNodeB_path	signal_strength
08126630	'99':2,'244':17,...	'99':0.154,'244':0.199,...

Given many available IMSIs, the dataset is then transformed from an IMSI-based to an event-based. The reason is that we want to predict the future location of a particular IMSI at a particular time. In this case, it is better to have the timestamp (event-based) as the main identifier of each entry of the data instead of the IMSI. So, for a particular timestamp,

the transformed dataset contains many IMSIs connected to many eNodeBs, but one IMSI is only allowed to connect to one eNodeB. The duration an IMSI remains connected to one eNodeB before switching to another is called a timeslot, as used in equation 1.

To provide a better context for each event, we then enrich the dataset with additional features, i.e.:

- `enode_1-enode_4`: The history of 4 previous connected eNodeBs.
- `time_1-time_4`: The timeslot of each connection.
- `sig_st`: Signal strength of that particular connection to the target eNodeB.
- `imsi`: The IMSI of the connected UE of the target eNodeB.
- `neigh_1-neigh_4`: Top four neighboring eNodeBs of the currently connected eNodeB.
- `early_morning, morning, noon, evening, and night`: Categorizing each timestamp into five different bins.
- `home_enb`: A home eNodeB where a particular IMSI stays connected the longest.

The enriched features are included in the final input variable, represented as x : `{enode_1, enode_2, enode_3, enode_4, time_1, time_2, time_3, time_4, sig_st, imsi, home_enb, early_morn, morning, noon, evening, night, neigh_1, neigh_2, neigh_3, neigh_4}`

The dataset is subsequently employed to construct a model that predicts the binned timeslot (\hat{s}), during which a UE maintains a connection to a specific eNodeB (\hat{l}). Note that the timeslot is binned to reduce the effect of small differences in continuous values, which are of less importance. Also, as the timeslot is the time spent on each eNodeB before moving to another location, classifying binned values is simpler than classifying the continuous values of many different UEs. This comes at the cost of rounding up each value to the respective range in the binned position. Note that a round-down is possible, but the resource will be allocated less than needed.

C. Finding the optimum time budget

Given the discussion in section IV, setting a suitable time budget for the model selection is important. In particular, it is more important for the retraining task in C3 because it is triggered when the accuracy of the prediction is low, while at the same time, the NWDAF is serving the subscribed NFs. On the other hand, for the initial model selection in C1, one would be able to spend as much time as possible due to the model not yet being operational. In this section, we discuss how we set the time budget for all the strategies A, B1, and B2 in relation to the initial and retraining task.

To start with, we explore how different time budgets impact prediction accuracy when the training set is not poisoned, i.e., consisting exclusively of legitimate UEs. We vary the time budget from 1 to 10 minutes and observe the changes in accuracy over the three different AutoML frameworks mentioned in section II-A: Auto-sklearn, FLAML, and AutoGluon.

Fig. 2. Time budget to the accuracy

Resource-wise, it is not feasible to test a very large number of different frameworks. We have chosen to work with these three as they give a good representation of different AutoML algorithms and use fundamental different optimizations and search spaces as shown in table I.

Then, we pick the smallest time budget once the values start to converge among the three frameworks. It would be possible to pick a longer time, but a shorter time budget is desired (as the time taken to iterate the process in Figure 1 is also shorter), especially during the retraining period in C3.

Figure 2 illustrates this relationship, showing a marked increase in accuracy in the initial runs, with a convergence over all the frameworks around the 6-minute mark. After this, the accuracy among the frameworks does not have a significant difference. To this end, we standardized the minimum time budget to get a meaningful result and obtain a performant model: 6 minutes. This is applied to both strategies A and B1 (for simplicity, let's call them TA and TB1, respectively). In A, TA is used in both C1 and C3, but in B1, TB1 is used only in C1 as the retraining in B1 uses the same selected model picked initially. Note that this is the minimum amount of time to be spent in model selection using AutoML to select the best-performing model. In these experiments, however, different datasets might yield different minimum time budget requirements. Adversary knowing the information of applied time budget to the training strategy could trigger the retraining phase more frequently, resulting in a never-ending cycle of retraining, which might affect the NWDAF's performance. Such a case is out of the scope of this paper and left for future investigation.

For a longer time budget in B2, we heuristically set it to be 10x the minimum time previously mentioned. Thus, the time budget for B2 is 60 minutes; we call it TB2 (used only in C1). Note that there is no long time budget for strategy A because spending longer time during C3 in strategy A is undesired, especially when the accuracy of the prediction is, at the same time, low. Using TA, TB1, and TB2, we explore

the operator’s options for preserving the NWDAF’s model prediction accuracy to the best possible extent. Our ultimate goal is to provide recommendations on which strategy to pursue for mobile operators facing similar issues in the future.

D. Attack on the training set

Given the pre-processed data and the minimum time budget mentioned earlier, we investigate the impact of the attacks on the hypothetical operators with the strategies A, B1, and B2. As the operator is assumed to be unable to distinguish the adversarial UEs, we investigate the effect of data poisoning during retraining. The poisoning is performed with an increasing proportion of adversarial UEs to the total number of legitimate UEs in the network, i.e., as there are 10000 legitimate UEs and 50 to 1000 adversarial UEs, the attack is performed with the proportion of 0.005 to 0.1 adversarial UEs to the total legitimate UEs. The interval of 50 is selected to provide a granular understanding of how the NWDAF’s performance is affected as the number of adversarial UEs increases within this range. To make a fair comparison, the configuration is kept to be as basic as possible for each framework we run. The following is the detail of the run on each strategy:

1) *A*: For each proportion of adversarial UEs, the retraining task with AutoML is performed five times, and then the mean and the standard deviation of the accuracy are calculated. Since AutoML is involved, each run for this strategy yields a different model and hyperparameters.

2) *B1 and B2*: For each proportion of adversarial UEs, the retraining task is performed five times with the same model selection as selected by the initial training, i.e., the same model but with different training data. The initial training for the model selection still involves AutoML with a time budget of 6 minutes for B1 and 60 minutes for B2. In the end, the mean and the standard deviation of the accuracy for each proportion of adversarial UEs are calculated.

E. Results

Given the attack previously explained, we draw the line plots of the prediction accuracy relative to the proportion of adversarial UEs in the network. The line plots in figures 3, 4, and 5 display two key pieces of information. The X-axis shows the ratio of adversarial UEs to the total legitimate UEs available in the network. On the Y-axis, the accuracy corresponds to each of these ratios.

Given the 6 minutes time budget explained in VII-C, it is clear that retraining the poisoned data with the AutoML frameworks for each retraining occasion (scenario A) is not enough to keep the accuracy desirable and cannot be generalized as the solution. While FLAML shows a slight decrease over the x-axis, AutoSklearn shows a significant decrease as the proportion of adversarial UEs increases. On the other hand, AutoGluon shows a more stable accuracy even though the accuracy value is around 42% regardless of the proportion of the adversarial UEs. The strategy A for FLAML and AutoSklearn shows a considerable variance compared to the

Fig. 3. The proportion of adversarial UEs on the accuracy of the retrained model using FLAML AutoML framework.

Fig. 4. The proportion of adversarial UEs on the accuracy of the retrained model using Auto-sklearn AutoML framework.

rest of the strategies. The variability of the accuracy could be attributed to the way the frameworks explore the model space, i.e., (i) Each run may start with a different random state, leading to different paths in the search for the optimal model, and (ii) The frameworks employ a cost-effective search strategy that balances between exploring different models and exploiting the best-performing models. This strategy can involve probabilistic decisions that might differ from one run to another. However, the accuracy is generally dropped (FLAML and AutoSklearn) or already low (AutoGluon) even when the model is newly selected for each proportion of adversarial UEs. In this case, following the self-correction policy [37] does not suit the situation, particularly when the proportion of the adversarial UEs is high.

Maintaining the original model and retraining it with poisoned data helps to keep the accuracy stable. Specifically, in scenario B1, all evaluated frameworks manage to maintain their accuracy levels, even as the share of adversarial UEs

Fig. 5. The proportion of adversarial UEs on the accuracy of the retrained model using AutoGluon AutoML framework.

increases. However, FLAML and AutoSklearn achieve higher accuracy compared to AutoGluon under these conditions. AutoGluon, in contrast, performs poorly, with its accuracy being worse than random guessing from the start. This reveals two key insights: firstly, having up to a 10% proportion of adversarial UEs does not significantly affect model performance in B1, despite the training data being poisoned with an increasing number of adversarial UEs. Secondly, in this specific case, AutoSklearn and FLAML outperform AutoGluon in developing a more accurate model, even though all frameworks manage to maintain consistent accuracy as the proportion of adversarial UEs increases.

However, it is clear from all the figures that B2 is the most robust scenario among all the strategies. Of all the frameworks, not only does B2 demonstrate the highest accuracy in comparison to the other scenarios, but it also maintains this accuracy consistently, even when the training data is incrementally poisoned. This is attributable to (i) a more extensive search and (ii) better hyperparameter tuning. The former allows AutoML to try out more models and a wider range of hyperparameters. This increases the likelihood of finding a model that generalizes better to unseen data, even when the data is poisoned with a larger proportion of adversarial UEs. The latter means AutoML can spend a longer time tuning the hyperparameters of each model. Hyperparameter tuning is critical for getting the best performance out of a machine learning model, and more time can lead to more precise tuning, resulting in a more robust model, even in the presence of adversarial data points.

While our results demonstrate that the B2 strategy, which involves an extensive initial AutoML search followed by retraining with the same model and hyperparameters on updated data, provides the best resilience against data poisoning attacks, it is important to consider the potential limitations. Although the B2 strategy updates the model with new data during retraining, it may not fully capture the context drift in the legitimate user data over time, as the model architecture

and hyperparameters remain fixed. As the mobility patterns of legitimate users evolve, the fixed model might not be able to adapt optimally to these changes, potentially leading to a gradual decrease in prediction accuracy for those users.

To mitigate this issue, periodic retraining using AutoML on carefully filtered data could help discover new model architectures and hyperparameters that better adapt to evolving legitimate user patterns while still maintaining robustness against attacks. Additionally, employing unsupervised anomaly detection techniques to identify and isolate potential adversarial data points before retraining could allow the model to benefit from updates that capture context drift more effectively while minimizing the impact of data poisoning. Future research should explore methods to balance the need for model adaptability with robustness against data poisoning attacks in the context of NWDAF mobility prediction to provide mobile network operators with strategies that optimize both factors.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates different AutoML frameworks for data poisoning of mobility data. When the adversarial UEs are not promptly identified and excluded from the training dataset, the quality of the mobility predictions for legitimate UEs deteriorates. This is particularly true if the trajectory model's retraining process is not robust enough. We show that while AutoML frameworks are effective in initial model selection, their efficiency during retraining is significantly challenged by the presence of adversarial mobility data. Extensive exploration of the model space and meticulous hyperparameter tuning at the beginning, as shown in operator B2, displayed a marked improvement in maintaining prediction accuracy, even when the model is fed with adversarial data points during the retraining phase.

Our study suggests that while automating model selection in the retraining phase is handy, the fact that the model owner has a limited time to train a newer model makes it problematic, especially when faced with adversarial data points. For future mobile network operations, our research recommends that mobile operators optimize the use of AutoML only during the initial training phase when NWDAF has not been deployed. This is to ensure that the operator gets the best trajectory model without worrying about the time budget, as shown by B2. Hence, even when the operator is being attacked by adversarial UEs, poisoned training data does not harm the overall system performance.

Future works include exploring the same strategy using real-world datasets from an actual NWDAF deployment. This is needed to validate our conclusion in a real-world scenario. While we only explore Auto-sklearn, FLAML, and AutoGluon, we find that other frameworks likely show similar trends, but still, a scrutinization is needed to confirm our hypothesis. Also, with a larger resource, one might be able to find the correlation between how much time is required to keep the accuracy desirable if the operator wants to stick with the scenario A.

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